

Vibrational fiber photometry: label-free and reporter-free minimally invasive Raman spectroscopy deep in the mouse brain

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Abstract

Optical approaches to monitor neural activity are transforming neuroscience, owing to a fast-evolving palette of genetically encoded molecular reporters. However, the field still requires robust and label-free technologies to monitor the multifaceted biomolecular changes accompanying brain development, aging or disease. Here, we propose vibrational fiber photometry as a low invasive method for label-free monitoring the bio-molecular content of arbitrarily deep regions of the mouse brain *in vivo* through spontaneous Raman spectroscopy. Using a tapered fiber probe as thin as 1 μm at its tip, we reveal the cytoarchitecture of the mouse brain, monitor molecular alterations caused by traumatic brain injury, as well as detecting markers of brain metastasis with high accuracy. We view our approach, which introduces a deep learning algorithm to suppress probe background, as a promising complement to the existing palette of tools for the optical interrogation of neural function, with application to fundamental and preclinical investigations of the brain and other organs.

Main text

Introduction

In the past two decades, optical approaches have emerged as a prominent paradigm to investigate brain functions *in vivo*¹. This versatile set of methods records neural activity using genetically encoded, fluorescent molecular reporters of membrane voltage and neurochemicals concentration, such as calcium or neuromodulators²⁻⁵. As this technological framework is reaching its maturity, there is growing agreement that a comprehensive investigation of brain functions should consider the multifaceted complexity of the brain as a multi-physical system⁶, including an assessment of the bio-molecular composition of the targeted brain volumes. Capturing a detailed picture of the chemical composition of specific brain regions, with a strategy that can be integrated with the existing techniques, can be instrumental to understand the underlying molecular mechanisms of brain

48 functions and disease. Yet, the available optical methods struggle in providing such a comprehensive
49 view, as the broad excitation and emission spectra of the molecular reporters ultimately limit the
50 options for spectral multiplexing. This shortcoming is even more critical when dealing with the study
51 of deep brain regions, where even multiphoton microscopy methods fail to reach a high signal-to-
52 noise ratio.

53 Label-free approaches using inelastic scattering of light, such as vibrational spectroscopy based on
54 Raman scattering⁷, can alleviate this shortcoming by detecting spectral fingerprints of multiple
55 molecular targets with broad sensitivity. For example, vibrational spectroscopy signatures of the
56 variation of neuronal membrane potential⁸ or the glucose metabolism dynamics in living mice⁹ have
57 been measured through stimulated Raman scattering (SRS), enabling fast, high-resolution imaging
58 using coherent ultrafast laser pulses. In addition, Raman spectroscopy is gaining traction in
59 neurosurgery, where it is used to assess the surgical margin intraoperatively^{10,11}. In this context, SRS
60 imaging allows for ultrafast label-free histological assessment of freshly excised tissue sections^{12,13}.
61 Alternatively, multi-waveguide surgical probes are used to characterize the molecular composition of
62 the surgical region via spontaneous Raman spectroscopy¹⁰. Unfortunately, these solutions are
63 unsuitable for neuroscience laboratories because they require complex optical systems¹⁴, or they rely
64 on probes that are small relative to the human brain^{11,15,16}, but large for the brain of small rodents,
65 which are a vastly used model for several brain diseases. As a result, the application of label-free and
66 reporter-free vibrational spectroscopy in system neuroscience is still in its infancy and it presently
67 requires bulky multiple waveguides and exogenous reporters¹⁷.

68 This work presents a method for label-free and reporter-free molecular spectroscopy from wide
69 volumes in arbitrarily deep regions of the mouse brain through vibrational fiber photometry. The
70 method uses a minimally invasive probe to detect molecular fingerprints in the Raman spectrum
71 acquired from tissue extending around and along the probe (Fig. 1a). In the following, we demonstrate
72 both *ex vivo* and *in vivo* that this approach allows to: (i) assess the cytoarchitecture of the targeted
73 brain region, (ii) detect molecular signals arising from Traumatic Brain Injury (TBI), or (iii) identify
74 molecular signals linked with the occurrence of brain metastasis. To do so, we introduce an optical
75 architecture to retrieve vibrational signals from deep brain volumes using a bench-top arrangement
76 for high-spectral resolution, and a portable system designed and validated for use in neuroscience
77 laboratories. After characterizing the sensitive photometry volume, we show that molecular
78 information on the local cytoarchitecture of the mouse brain can be retrieved with minimal tissue
79 damage. Then, we demonstrate the relevance of the method by targeting two applications. Firstly, we
80 report on the detection and spectral characterization of localized alterations in the molecular
81 composition of subcortical brain regions generated by local brain metastasis, providing evidence of
82 robust and reliable diagnostics *ex vivo* and *in vivo*. Finally, we describe spatially diffuse variations in
83 the molecular composition of brain regions suffering acute lesions in a TBI model. To achieve these
84 results, we developed a deep learning (DL) analysis of Raman spectra¹⁸⁻²¹ to enhance the visibility
85 of spectral features masked by the strong fiber background (e.g. 900 cm^{-1} – 1300 cm^{-1} range), using a
86 versatile approach that is agnostic to the final processed data and dispenses with the need for extensive
87 training datasets from large cohort of animals (Fig. 1b).

88 In our view, vibrational fiber photometry in deep brain volumes offers an opportunity to augment the
89 information extracted from remote areas, placing the patterns of neural activity in context with the
90 molecular content of the local micro-environment. This capability is central to increase our
91 understanding on compelling open questions related to the neurochemical bases of neural function
92 and dysfunction, regarding the emerging evidence of brain-immune²² and brain-cancer²³ bidirectional
93 dynamics. The label-free nature of this technique in its combination with depth-enhanced optical
94 access, provided by tapered fiber probes, has potential to be applied in basic, pre-clinical and

95 translational neuroscience research, setting a technological path that will be viable to the brain and
96 other organs.

97 **Results**

98 **Deep brain wide volume vibrational fiber photometry with Tapered Fiber**

99 The application of Raman spectroscopy in endoscopic measurements is conventionally achieved
100 using multiple fibers to increase the recording volume and to separate excitation and collection
101 signals, discarding the probe's own Raman response. This scheme has been pursued in many
102 architectures, using multiple waveguides, bundles, or multi-core fibers to achieve a satisfactory
103 spectral sensitivity and, in some instances, cellular resolution²⁴. These approaches resulted in probes
104 with a spatial footprint in the order of a few mm, which are too bulky to be implanted deep in the
105 mouse brain without impactful tissue destruction.

106 To tackle this challenge, we exploit mode-division de-multiplexing properties in tapered optical fibers
107 (TFs)²⁵ to enlarge the collection volume without increasing the transversal size of the implant. Our
108 probes have a diameter of 225 μm at its widest and about 1 μm at the fiber tip. The tapered region
109 extends for ~ 2 mm from the flat section to the tip, resulting in an overall fiber length of ~ 4 cm, from
110 the back facet of the ferrule to the tip. The sharp profile of TFs reduces tissue reaction with respect
111 to standard fiber optics without jeopardizing robustness, as reported in previous works^{26,27}, and it
112 allows the bidirectional exchange of photons with the surrounding tissue, as previously exploited to
113 control and monitor neural activity with excitation and collection signals falling within the visible
114 range²⁷⁻²⁹. We observed that these properties can be extended into the near-infrared (NIR) range,
115 paving the way to the use of TF for low invasiveness Raman spectroscopy – here coined *vibrational*
116 *fiber photometry*. Our approach takes advantage from red shifted excitation wavelengths (e.g. 785
117 nm) to mitigate tissue autofluorescence and from co-localized collection in the so-called fingerprint
118 (FP, 800 – 1850 cm^{-1}) and high wavenumber (HW, 2800 – 3100 cm^{-1}) spectral ranges.

119 The volumes of tissue from which the TF collects information were modeled using a combination of
120 Ray Tracing and Montecarlo techniques in a numerical tissue phantom (see Methods). Fig. 1c shows
121 the normalized excitation and collection diagrams and the vibrational photometry diagram for a 2 mm
122 long tapered tip with 0.22 NA, 200 μm / 225 μm core/cladding outcoupling at 785 nm and collecting
123 at 885 nm (1440 cm^{-1}). The photometry diagram highlights that the TF collects a nearly uniform
124 vibrational signal along the optically active region of the cone. Extrapolating from previous works
125 for optogenetic stimulation, we forecast that the extent of these regions can potentially be tuned to
126 match the extent of target brain regions²⁵. The validation of the numerical model with the
127 experimental measurements of the excitation volume in the cortex of a fixed slice is shown in the
128 Supplementary Fig. 1.

129 To employ the TF probes for vibrational fiber photometry, we devised two custom Raman
130 microscopes, a bench-top and a portable system, that allow controlling a TF implant through minimal
131 lengths of waveguide to minimize the Raman background generated by the silica fiber. The benchtop
132 system was designed to obtain high signal-to-noise ratio and high spectral resolution in both FP and
133 HW spectral ranges, while the portable system was instead devised to be deployed in stereotaxic rigs
134 in neuroscience laboratories. Details on the two systems and on their validation are reported in
135 Supplementary Fig. 2.

136 Using the bench top system in the HW range, we measured the variations in the Raman spectra
137 acquired at increasing depth in the dorso-ventral (DV) direction of *ex vivo* naïve mouse brains (Fig.
138 1d, e, see Methods). The HW range is particularly suitable to extract information on the local
139 biomolecular profile^{30,31} since it contains strong vibrational bands associated with lipid and protein
140 content. These bands enjoy a larger Raman cross section than their counterparts in the FP range and
141 this effect compensates for the decrease in the detection efficiency of CCD cameras in the HW range

142 when using 785 nm excitation. As the TF travelled from cortical to subcortical brain regions (Fig.
143 1e), the Raman spectra in the HW range reflected the variations in the local molecular composition
144 ^{30,31}. The presence of cells' somas in cortical layers (from 0 mm to -1 mm in the DV axis) is
145 highlighted by strong protein bands (2930 cm⁻¹); lipid signatures (2845-2875 cm⁻¹) become more
146 prominent in deeper regions through the corpus callosum (CC), the fimbria of the Hippocampus (HP)
147 and myelinated regions around the Thalamus (TL) (e.g., from -1 mm to -2 mm and from -2 mm to -3
148 mm in the DV axis). These results, which are consistent with previous reports ³¹, confirm that
149 vibrational fiber photometry with TFs offers a convenient approach to assess the local chemical
150 composition of the brain parenchyma with negligible tissue displacement.

151 **Label free spectroscopy of deep brain metastasis**

152 The spectral features extracted from vibrational spectra offer an opportunity to detect brain
153 pathologies through the variations of molecular content. To demonstrate this, we focused on detecting
154 the presence of brain metastasis, the most frequent form of brain tumor, through vibrational fiber
155 photometry. Previous works have reported on the detection of melanoma brain metastasis in the
156 mouse using large probes hovering above the exposed parenchyma³². We confirmed these results by
157 acquiring Raman spectra, in a conventional configuration, from a murine model of melanoma brain
158 metastasis (B16/F10-BrM)³³ focusing on the spectral differences between the tumor core and the
159 contralateral region, such as an increase in the melanin bands at 980 cm⁻¹, 1400 cm⁻¹ and 1590 cm⁻¹,
160 a reduction in the amide bands at 1260 cm⁻¹ and 1660 cm⁻¹, a reduction in lipid bands at 1290 cm⁻¹,
161 1440 cm⁻¹, 2850 cm⁻¹ and an increase that we tentatively attributed to cellular proliferation at 1525
162 cm⁻¹ and 2930 cm⁻¹ (Supplementary Fig. 2).

163 Next, we evaluated whether high detection accuracy could be obtained using a thin neural probe
164 reaching subcortical regions to provide information on the depth of the lesion. We identified relevant
165 spectral signatures of melanoma brain metastasis³³ through a systematic *ex vivo* study in metastatic
166 (n=3) and control (n=3) brains where we recorded the Raman signal at progressively deeper locations.
167 In metastatic brains we targeted the tumor core, its contralateral position on the medio-lateral axis
168 and one or more locations on the lesion's periphery; similar positions were measured in the control
169 brains (see Methods). Raman spectra collected in brain regions with metastatic colonization (Tumor,
170 magenta), cancer free regions in the contralateral hemisphere (Clat, cyan) and controls (Ctrl, olive
171 green) in the FP and HW ranges are shown in Fig. 2 a, b (average \pm standard deviation). A clear
172 differentiation emerges when computing the difference between the average spectra in metastatic
173 (magenta) or healthy (cyan) regions minus the average spectrum in control brains (Fig. 2 c, d). The
174 data highlight several spectral signatures that unambiguously correlate with cancer colonization of
175 brain tissue: the prominence of peaks compatible with melanin pigment in cancer cells at 1400 cm⁻¹
176 and 1590 cm⁻¹ (Fig. 2 a, c) ^{32,34}, a diminished signal in the FP lipid and Amide I bands (1440 cm⁻¹ and
177 1660 cm⁻¹, Fig. 2a, c) ^{11,32}, and a diminished signal of CH (Carbon-Hydrogen) bands in the HW range
178 (2850-3000 cm⁻¹, Fig. 2 b, d)^{11,16}. These features are consistent with the ones measured from the
179 brain surface (Supplementary Fig. 2). However, the suppression of HW signals (where the silica
180 background has a negligible intensity) appears to be more pronounced in deep tissue regions than in
181 the superficial layers.

182 These observations are corroborated by Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The three most
183 informative components (PC1, PC2 and PC3) in the FP and HW were classified into categories by a
184 density-based algorithm (Fig. 2 e, f respectively; see Methods, and Supplementary Fig. 3). The PCA
185 predictions were compared to the ground truth of the histological analysis (Fig. 2 g, h and
186 Supplementary Fig. 4). The comparison between PCA predictions and histological ground truth
187 across the full dataset resulted in a sensitivity of 91% (60%), a specificity of 90% (100%) and an
188 accuracy of 91% (82%) in the FP (HW) range. A summary heatmap of PCA prediction against
189 histology is shown in Fig. 2i.

190 We then translated the study to *in vivo* conditions and measured Raman spectra at multiple locations
191 and depths in metastatic (n=4) and control (n=3) anesthetized animals. The TF was inserted in the
192 tumor core and in its contralateral locations in metastatic brains, and in both hemispheres in control

193 brains. All animals survived the insertion and were sacrificed after the experiments. Fig. 2 j, k show
194 the average spectra obtained in the tumor core (magenta), contralateral hemisphere (cyan) and control
195 brains (olive) for the FP and HW range, respectively, as extracted from the data (a single spectrum
196 was acquired across the FP and HW range for technical reasons, see Methods). Fig. 2 l, m display the
197 average spectral differences for both ranges. As in the *ex vivo* analysis, we observed a stronger
198 melanin signal at 1400 cm^{-1} and 1590 cm^{-1} , and a weaker signal in the lipid bands at 1440 cm^{-1} and
199 amide I band at 1660 cm^{-1} , and a strong suppression in the high-wavenumbers, consistent with
200 previous *in vivo* results with intraoperative non-penetrating probes¹¹. Also, we recorded an increased
201 signal in the range 1525 cm^{-1} – 1575 cm^{-1} in metastatic regions, consistent with previous reports on the
202 Raman signatures of cellular proliferation³⁵.

203 The PCA analysis of the *in vivo* data highlighted two clearly separated clusters (Fig. 2n) (see
204 Methods). Looking at the composition of these clusters following the insertion position (Fig. 2o), we
205 observed that the measurement in the contralateral hemisphere (cyan dots) are co-clustered with the
206 measurements in the controls (green dots) and are clearly separated from the measurement in the
207 tumor (magenta dots). Interestingly, measurements taken in the vicinity of the metastasis are
208 classified as either positive or negative for cancer (mustard dots). This is most probably due to the
209 heterogenous nature of the peritumoral regions, an area of great biological and clinical significance
210 since the presence of invasive fronts has been correlated with a higher propensity of post-surgery
211 cancer relapse^{36–38}. Due to the small cross section of the TFs, it was not possible to reconstruct all the
212 insertion tracks. While the probe can penetrate the brain to the target point without bending, the
213 volume of displaced tissue is small and the track is lost after the fiber is extracted. Within the few
214 cases where we reconstructed the insertion track, we observed that when the probe approaches the
215 metastasis without penetrating it (Extended Data 1) the related spectra are classified as healthy
216 (orange dots in Fig. 2o).

217 We then set out to access information in the lower FP range using a Convolutional Neural Network
218 (CNN) to isolate the contributions of brain Raman signals from the fiber background. The CNN
219 consists of a cascaded U-NET trained on datasets based on the fiber background and synthetically
220 augmented with simulated Raman signals, polynomial baselines, and noise components (see Methods
221 and Supplementary Fig. 4). First, we validated the algorithm using data acquired with the benchtop
222 system against Raman spectra acquired without the fiber (Supplementary Fig. 4). Second, we
223 compared the results obtained in *ex vivo* brains before and after the CNN-processing, finding that the
224 network enhances the visibility of the salient spectral features while discarding the fiber background
225 (Supplementary Fig. 4). Then, we applied the CNN to *in vivo* data (Fig. 2 q, r) extending the spectral
226 range ($900 - 1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$) to identify a strong peak attributed to melanin at 980 cm^{-1} and confirming the
227 increase of the melanin band at 1400 cm^{-1} , the suppression of the lipid band at 1440 cm^{-1} and amide
228 I band at 1660 cm^{-1} , and a combined increase at 1160 cm^{-1} , and in the ranges $1350\text{--}1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and
229 $1500 - 1550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ that might be linked to blood extravasation following disruption of the blood brain
230 barrier by the metastasis³⁹. The signal increase in the range $1525\text{ cm}^{-1} - 1550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been previously
231 assigned to cellular proliferation³⁵. Conversely, we did not observe a clear peak at 1590 cm^{-1} where
232 we instead recorded a decrease of signal in the metastatic region. This observation is not in agreement
233 with the *ex vivo* data and we believe it is an artifact of the CNN-processing due to the limited optical
234 performances of the portable spectrometer. As the Raman signal in the $1550\text{--}1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range sits on
235 top of a relatively strong silica band, the algorithm fails in discriminating the two components.
236 However, the *ex vivo* data confirm that this shortcoming can be readily addressed using a spectrometer
237 with better resolution and sensitivity (Supplementary Fig. 4). The information disclosed by the CNN-
238 processing allowed the identification of an additional PCA cluster halfway between the ones assigned
239 to healthy and cancer tissue (Fig. 2s). This cluster appears to primarily associate with spectra acquired
240 in tissue at the periphery of the metastasis (Fig. 2t). The PCA-vs-insertion summary (Fig. 2u)
241 confirms that the CNN processing improves PCA results towards discriminating healthy regions areas
242 within or around the metastasis.

243 Overall, we observed that the vibrational signatures provide robust discrimination of healthy brain
244 regions from melanoma brain metastasis. Although different brain regions are characterized by
245 different Raman spectra³¹, these differences are smaller than the ones observed against cancer invaded
246 regions, as shown by PCA. However, our data are limited to advanced metastatic formations and
247 early-stage neo-formations might exhibit more nuanced spectral features.

248 *Ratiometric segmentation for single-spectrum diagnostics*

249 To further confirm results, we devised a ratiometric analysis that achieves rapid classification of the
250 probed tissue with a single spectrum^{40,41}. We defined four different figures of merit (FoMs),
251 calculated on the raw Raman spectra $S(s)$ (where s indicates the Raman shift) (Extended Data 2).
252 Here, R1 is defined as $R1 = S(1400\text{ cm}^{-1})/S(1440\text{ cm}^{-1})$, reflecting the intensity ratio between
253 the peaks of melanin at 1400 cm^{-1} and lipids at 1440 cm^{-1} ; R2, is defined as $R2 =$
254 $S(1440\text{ cm}^{-1})/S(1800\text{ cm}^{-1})$, mirroring the intensity ratio between the lipid band at 1440 cm^{-1} and
255 autofluorescence at 1800 cm^{-1} ; R3, is calculated as $R3 = S(1800\text{ cm}^{-1})/S(2100\text{ cm}^{-1})$, linked with
256 the presence of autofluorescence in the Raman silent region; and finally R4, is calculated as $R4 =$
257 $S'(2847) + S'(3100)$ on the first derivative of the spectrum $S' = \partial S/\partial s$, to extract information on
258 the strength of the onset and offset of CH bands respectively at 2847 cm^{-1} and 3100 cm^{-1} (Extended
259 Data 2). We observed that the probability distributions of FoM values correlate with the histological
260 classification of ex vivo brain samples (Fig. 3 a-d). Also, the scores measured in metastatic regions
261 deviate from those obtained in controls and from the healthy tissue in metastatic brains (Fig. 3 e-h).
262 The discriminative ability of these FoMs is corroborated by having an Area Under the Curve (AUC)
263 of the Receiver Operator Characteristic (ROC) comparable to those reported for Raman probes
264 intraoperatively¹¹. We obtained an AUC of 0.96, 0.95, 0.95 and 0.92 for R1, R2, R3 and R4
265 respectively (Fig. 3 i-l).

266 **Label-free spectroscopy of diffuse molecular alterations: TBI**

267 Deep brain vibrational spectroscopy offers a privileged channel to measure biochemical alterations
268 diffused across different regions underlying impairment of brain functions, as it is the case for
269 neurotrauma. To expand applicability, we sought to test changes associated to a murine model of
270 traumatism (TBI model, see methods). We thus collected Raman spectra through a TF inserted at
271 several depths in the lesion core (TBI), in the lesion periphery (pTBI) and in the contralateral
272 hemisphere (Clat), in whole brains ($n=3$) *ex vivo*. Fig. 4 a, b show the average spectra obtained for
273 the FP and HW range respectively. Regions were classified by histology (see Methods). The
274 difference between spectra for TBI minus the contralateral side are shown in Fig. 4 c,d (FP and HW
275 range respectively), while Fig. 4 e,f show the same for periTBI minus contralateral side in both ranges.
276 Similar conclusions can be reached with the CNN algorithm to isolate the Raman signal from the
277 fiber background in the FP region. Consistent with previous results, Fig. 4g shows the average spectra
278 after the CNN processing for the lesion core (TBI), in the lesion periphery (pTBI) and in the
279 contralateral hemisphere (Clat) (see difference spectra in Fig. 4 h, i).

280 With both approaches, we observed a modulation of the signal in several vibrational bands associated
281 with lipid and protein content. Our results are consistent with previous reports using Raman
282 spectroscopy on the brain surface or in brain slices from TBI models³⁹. We found that lipid bands at
283 1300 cm^{-1} , 1440 cm^{-1} (Fig. 4 a, c, e) and 2850 cm^{-1} (Fig. 4 b, d, f) are reduced in periTBI and TBI
284 regions with respect to contralateral measurements. At the same time, a sizeable depletion of the 1660
285 cm^{-1} band, linked with amide I vibration of proteins and C=C stretching of lipids³⁹, emerges in the
286 TBI and periTBI location (Fig. 4 c, e). These alterations are consistent with the histological
287 observation of cell loss, shown by bisbenzimidazole staining of cell nuclei (Fig. 4j), and demyelination
288 as evaluated by FluoroMyelin (Fig. 4k) in TBI and periTBI regions as opposed to the contralateral
289 hemisphere. At the same time, the lesion core returned a stronger signal in the 1350 cm^{-1} – 1400 cm^{-1}
290 range together with an increase at 1620 cm^{-1} (Fig. 4c). We forward the hypothesis that these features
291 are linked with blood extravasation based on direct evidence revealed here by IgG staining (Fig. 4l)
292 combined with previous association of these bands with blood serum components³⁹. Nonetheless, we
293 also remark that this spectral feature is suppressed in the CNN-processed spectra. This inconsistency

294 follows a similar observation discussed in the application to melanoma brain metastasis, where larger
295 spectral features already appeared less likely to be processed as Raman signal by the CNN. While
296 this effect might testify for a genuine difference in the physical origin of the signals, we concede that
297 it might be due to an overly conservative choice on the width parameters of the synthetic Raman peak
298 used in the network training (see Methods).

299 Looking instead to the HW range, we observed a moderate increase of the Raman signal at the 2940
300 cm^{-1} (Fig. 4 d). Although of modest strength, this band has been previously observed in a model of
301 inflammation in retinal organotypic cultures and linked to cytochrome C and phenylalanine⁴². Both
302 constructs have biophysical relevance for TBI as cytochrome C is involved in immune-drive
303 apoptosis⁴³ and phenylalanine has been previously identified as potential biomarker for severe TBI
304 in murine models⁴⁴. Considering the converging evidence of the onset of neuroinflammation in the
305 TBI region obtained via immuno-histological imaging against Cox-2 (Fig. 4 m), these results open
306 an interesting perspective on the potential use of vibrational spectroscopy to monitor immune
307 response in deep brain regions.

308 **Technological perspectives**

309 Based on our results, it may be beneficial to precisely control the extent of the tissue region from
310 which the Raman signal is collected. A precise control on the targeted volume of tissue can be
311 obtained by micro-structuring a metal layer deposited on the TF tip, fabricating optical windows that
312 confine light delivery and collection (see Methods)⁴⁵. A probe with a $100\ \mu\text{m} \times 50\ \mu\text{m}$ optical window
313 opened on a TF coated with a thin layer of gold (Fig. 5a) can acquire enough signal to differentiate
314 healthy brain tissue from a melanoma brain metastasis (Fig. 5b, c). As observed with the uncoated
315 fiber, healthy tissue has a stronger contribution in the lipid bands ($1440\ \text{cm}^{-1}$, $1660\ \text{cm}^{-1}$) while
316 metastatic tissue has a strong signal in the melanin band ($1400\ \text{cm}^{-1}$) and a smaller signal in the lipid
317 band ($1440\ \text{cm}^{-1}$).

318 Unlike recent reports on Surface Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS) from TFs decorated with
319 noble metal nanoparticles⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸, we did not observe a surface enhancement of the Raman signal linked
320 to the gold layer. We believe this is because the smooth gold layer is not as efficient in enhancing
321 Raman scattering and it is thick enough (150 nm) to act as a shield for the scattered photons. The
322 signal collected from the micro-machined optical window is therefore spontaneous Raman scattering
323 from the adjacent tissue.

324 **Discussion**

325 We have presented an approach to monitor the molecular content in arbitrarily deep regions of the
326 mouse brain using label-free vibrational fiber photometry with a thin optical implant. In our view,
327 this strategy will provide a substantial augmentation to established approaches for controlling and
328 monitoring neural activity, opening paths to capture a more comprehensive picture of the neuro-
329 chemical bases of brain function and dysfunction. To ease application, we developed a portable
330 system for use in standard stereotaxic rigs that provides robust performances despite some tradeoffs
331 in spectral resolution and sensitivity. Also, we propose a versatile deep learning approach to mitigate
332 the fiber background problem, which can be readily implemented across a broad class of studies,
333 provided that the training dataset is thoughtfully constructed. Although our method cannot yet achieve
334 the spatial resolution provided by endoscopes with larger diameters¹⁵, we envision that ultra-thin
335 neural Raman endoscopes are within reach owing to recent progress in miniaturized optical systems
336 and wavefront shaping through turbid multimode fibers^{26,49,50}. Thus, our results together with recent
337 advances in micro- and nano-neuro-technologies enabling multimodal characterization of brain
338 circuits⁵¹⁻⁵³, can help devising optical neural probes using nanoscale phenomena for optical control
339 and for enhanced detection of neurochemicals⁵⁴. This emerging class of techniques, granting the
340 possibility of capturing a comprehensive molecular picture of the local brain micro-environment *in*
341 *vivo* and *in depth*, will provide a powerful toolbox to investigate the complex interplay between brain
342 cancer progression and neural activity in the emerging field of cancer neuroscience^{55,56}.

343 In this direction, the combination of *label free* volumetric detection and minimal footprint discloses
344 an exciting potential for monitoring the response to treatment (e.g. chemotherapy or radiotherapy) or

345 for intraoperative assessment of tumor resection margins below the tissue surface. At the same time,
346 vibrational photometry can yield unique information on a broad range of more elusive molecular
347 alterations that can potentially shed light on the interaction between the brain and the immune system,
348 not only in the context of brain disease but also in relation to physiological processes such as
349 development or ageing²². Strikingly, our tools can be applied to the growing field of functional *ex*
350 *vivo* preparations (e.g. organotypic slices and organoids) to boost personalized biomedical
351 applications⁵⁷⁻⁵⁹.
352

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372 **Author Contribution Statement**

373 F.Pisano and M.M.M. are co-first authors. M.S.A., E.C. M.K., M.P. contributed equally and are listed
374 in alphabetical order. F.G., F.D.A., M.d.V., L.M.P., M.V., F.Pisanello jointly supervised the work
375 and are co-last authors on this work. F.Pisano, M.P., M.G., A.B., F.T., F.d.A., M.d.V., F. Pisanello
376 developed the benchtop Raman system. M.P., M.S.A., F.T., F.Pisano, F. Pisanello developed the
377 portable Raman system. M.M.M., M.V. T.J.P., L.M.P. tested the portable system. L.S. developed the
378 TF for the Raman application. M.S.A., M.P., F.Pisano performed the *ex vivo* experiments. M.M.M.,
379 P.B., M.V. developed the melanoma brain metastasis model and performed *in vivo* experiments. E.C.,
380 T.J.P., L.M.P developed the traumatic brain injury model and performed immuno-histochemistry.
381 T.J.P, E.C., M.S.A, L.M.P performed *in vivo* traumatic brain injury experiments and collected Raman
382 data. F.Pisano, M.S.A., M.P., M.B., A.B., L.C. F.G., F.Pisanello developed and performed the data
383 analysis. M.K. developed and performed the deep learning network and analysis. M.B, M.G., F.
384 Pisano developed and performed the numerical simulations. F.Pisano, A.B. fabricated the micro-
385 structured probes and performed the experiments. F.G. developed and performed the PCA analysis.
386 F. Pisano, F.d.A., M.d.V., L.M.P., M.V., F.Pisanello conceived the application of vibration fiber
387 photometry in deep brain regions. F.Pisano and F. Pisanello conceptualized the work with
388 contributions from all authors. F.Pisano drafted the manuscript and prepared the figures. All authors
389 edited the manuscript.

390 **Competing interests statement**

391 L.S., M.D.V. and F.Pisanello. are founders and hold private equity in Optogenix, a company that
392 develops, produces, and sells technologies to deliver light into the brain. L.S. and M. P. are employed
393 by Optogenix. F.Pisano has been employed by Optogenix. Products of Optogenix have been used in
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395 authors declare no competing interest.
396